

FUNDAMENTAL ANALYSIS OF RELIANCE INDUSTRIES LIMITED

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Abstract – Fundamental analysis are associated with the economic health of a company or the financial position of a company. A company is supposed to be considered as healthy with its good fundamentals and also if it is growing at a nice pace, generating profits consecutively, has limited debts and abundant cash to meet its current obligations. The present work is an outcome of “A study on fundamental analysis of Reliance Industries Limited”. The study was carried out for the period of five years during 2020-21 to 2024-25 to analyze the financial performance of the Reliance Industries Ltd. The tools used for analysis is ratio analysis and the trend percentages. The findings from the analysis were discussed in detail, suggestions for corrective action like maintaining good solvency in order to meet short term and long term obligations were given wherever applicable.

Keywords – Fundamental analysis, ratios, trend percentages, Reliance Industries)..

I. INTRODUCTION

Reliance Industries Limited (RIL) company incorporated in 1973 by Dhirubhai Ambani headquartered in Mumbai Maharashtra, India is a fortune 500 company and the largest Indian Multinational Conglomerate holding over 200 subsidiary companies and numerous Associates currently led by Mr. Mukesh D Ambani. Reliance owns businesses across India mainly engaged in Energy, Petrochemicals, Textiles, Natural Resources, Retail, and Telecommunications, Entertainment and man media. RIL is the most profitable company in India, the largest listed company by market capitalization and by revenue. Revenue Breakup – Oil-to-Chemical business increased revenue by 11% of the revenue, Oil & Gas revenue increased by 3.2%, Retail increased revenue by 7.9 %, Digital Service increased revenue by 15.9%. The company's equity shares are listed on the National Stock Exchange of India Limited (NSE) and the BSE Limited. Its debt securities are listed at the Wholesale Debt Market (WDM) Segment of the National Stock Exchange of India Limited (NSE). The number of shares of RIL are approx. 6.44 billion. The promoter group, Ambani family, holds approx. 50.39% of the total shares whereas the remaining 49.61% shares are held by public shareholders, including FII and corporate bodies. Life Insurance Corporation of India is the largest non-promoter investor in the company, with 6.49% shareholding. Reliance announces global collaborations with tech giants, including Meta (formerly Facebook), Google, Intel, and Qualcomm. This follows Jio and Microsoft's long-term alliance announced in 2019 to accelerate India's digital transformation.

Reliance sets up India's first COVID-19 hospital in Mumbai along with the Brihanmumbai Municipal Corporation. Reliance's Jamnagar refinery re-engineers its process to produce over 1,000 MT of medical-grade oxygen per day, meeting the critical needs of about 1 in 10 COVID-19 patients across India. Reliance rolls out its free COVID-19 vaccination programme for employees, families, household members, and communities. Reliance Foundation provides over 85 million free meals to the

needy. Reliance extends medical, financial, and educational support to those severely affected by COVID-19. RIL Chairman and Managing Director Mukesh D. Ambani announces target of making Reliance net-zero carbon by 2035. Reliance announces the US\$ 10 billion New Energy business to bridge the green energy divide in India and globally. Reliance begins work on developing the Dhirubhai Ambani Green Energy Giga Complex on 5,000 acres in Jamnagar, which will be amongst the largest such integrated renewable energy manufacturing facilities in the world. Jio announces the launch of Jio True 5G—the world's most advanced standalone 5G service. Jio Financial Services forms JV with BlackRock to deliver digital financial solutions for India. Jio World Centre (JWC) opens in Mumbai, India, 2022. It is the country's largest and most prestigious multi-faceted destination, with spaces for business, commerce and culture. The Nita Ambani Cultural Centre (NACC) opens at JWC in 2023, bringing the best of arts and culture from India and the world. Jio World Plaza opens in Mumbai, setting the bar for top-end retail and entertainment experiences in India.

II. OBJECTIVES

□ The major objective of the study is to determine the Reliance Industries Ltd. fundamental analysis using Trend percentages.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research methodology involves specific techniques that are adopted in research process to collect, assemble and evaluate data. It defines those tools that are used to gather relevant information in a specific research study. It is the systematic investigation into and study of materials and sources in order to establish facts and reach new conclusions

Tools used for the analysis

Trend percentages used for the study.

IV. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The data used for the study is from secondary sources so that the accuracy may lack in this case.
- The study is confined to only 5 years of data that has been used for the fundamental analysis.i.e. from 2020-21 to 2024- 25.

V. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

J. Hema and V.Ariram (2016), “Fundamental analysis with special reference to pharmaceutical companies listed in NSE”, this study is focused on the fundamental analysis of three randomly selected pharmaceutical companies that are listed in the NSE. The data for the analysis is collected for a period of 5 years from 2011 to 2015. The fundamental analysis consists of three parts namely EIC (Economic, Industry& Company) analysis. Economic analysis the financial Ratio’s namely Earning per share(EPS), Dividend per share(DPS), Net profit margin and Debt to equity ratio were used as the tool to conclude the result of the study. Industrial analysis shows that the Indian Pharmaceutical industry has high growth rate. Company analysis revealed that Lupin and Torrent pharma are financially stable during the study period. The economic analysis indicates the factors that influence the security market.

Keerthi Gururaj Kulakarani and Gururaj Anand Kulkarani (2013-2014), “Fundamental analysis vs technical analysis: a choice of sectoral analysis”, the paper explores the analytical tools in evaluating the sectoral stocks. It makes a comparison on the fundamental analysis and the technical analysis to find out the importance of them in the decision of making investments in the securities. The study was conducted on the IT sectors, Automobile sectors, real estate sector, oil and natural gas sector and the banking sector of India. The period of the secondary data that are collected is limited to 1 year. Primary data are also used for the analysis. The study concludes that fundamental analysis is considered to be the most preferred analysis in choosing stocks to get higher returns. Real estate is the most preferred stock as per the result of the study.

A.S.Suresh (2013), “A study on the fundamental and technical analysis”, estimates the stock price changes by studying the forces operating in the overall economy, as well as influences peculiar to industries and the companies. This study helps in selecting the right time and the right securities for the investment. It predicts the direction of the national economy because economic activity affects the corporate profit, investors attitude and security prices. Fundamental analysis is made on the 3 phase approach that is the EIC (Economy, Industry, Company) approach. The technical analysis is done using Dow theory, charting, trends, moving average, relative strength, break-out theory. The study considers the risk and the return as the two most important characteristics of any investment. According to

the analysis, the objectives of the investors is specified as the maximization of return and minimization of risks

VI. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1.1 TREND PERCENTAGES OF CURRENT RATIO OF RIL

Year	Current ratio	Trend Percentage
2020-2021	1.34	100%
2021-2022	1.12	83.58%
2022-2023	1.07	79.85%
2023-2024	1.18	88.06%
2024-2025	1.1	82.09%

Interpretation

The current ratio of the Reliance Industries Ltd is not satisfying the standard of current ratio 2:1 which is considered as the healthy financial status of a company. But the Reliance’s current ratio have a decreasing trend from 1.34 to 1.1 1during the study period i.e., from 2020-21 to 2024-25. Thus the Reliance company is failing to payout the debt with its current assets. The liability of the Reliance Company is increasing than the assets of the company over the last 5 years.

Figure 1.1 Trend Percentage of Current Ratio

Table 1.2. TREND PERCENTAGES OF SALES OF RIL

Year	Sales (in Crores)	Trend Percentage
2020-2021	245,667.00	100
2021-2022	423,703.00	172.47

2022-2023	528,315.00	215.05
2023-2024	534,534.00	217.58
2024-2025	517,349.00	210.59

Interpretation

By using trend analysis, it has been found that the sales of Reliance Industries Limited are on increasing trend from 2020-21 to 2023-24 whereas in FY 2024-25, the sales for RIL decreased by 3.21% compared to previous year during 2023-24.

Figure 1.2 Trend Percentage of Sales

Table 1.3 TREND PERCENTAGES OF PROFIT AFTER TAX OF RIL

Year	PAT	Trend Percentage
2020-2021	27,640	100
2021-2022	39,084	141.40
2022-2023	43,017	155.63
2023-2024	42,042	152.11
2024-2025	35,262	127.58

Figure 1.3 Trend Percentage of PAT

Interpretation

The profit after tax of RIL experiences an increasing trend consecutively for a period of four financial years i.e. from

2020-21 to 2023-24. This indicates that the net profit of RIL is in a positive direction. But during the last year i.e. 2024-25 PAT decreased by 16% compared to previous year 2023-24.

Table 1.4 TREND PERCENTAGES OF DIVIDEND PER SHARE OF RIL

Year	Dividend Per Share	Trend Percentage
2020-2021	7	100
2021-2022	8	114.29
2022-2023	9	128.57
2023-2024	10	142.86
2024-2025	5.5	78.57

Interpretation

It is interpreted from the above table that Reliance Industries Limited’s dividend per share (DPS) has an increasing trend Consecutively from 2020-2021 to 2023-2024 whereas the DPS for the FY i.e., 2024-25 fallen by 45% compared to its previous FY 2023-24.

Figure 1.4 Trend Percentage of Dividend per Share

Table 1.5 TREND PERCENTAGES OF SHARE VALUE OF RIL

Year	Per Share value	Trend Percentage
2020-2021	33.29	100
2021-2022	2.25	6.76

2022-2023	49.3	148.09
2023-2024	31.07	93.33
2024-2025	1.21	3.63

Figure 1.5 Trend Percentage of per Share

Interpretation:

It is interpreted from the above table that Reliance Industries Limited’s per share has been found fluctuating during the study period whereas the trend percentage of share value drastically fallen down during last year FY i.e., 2024-25 by 96.11% compared to previous year FY i.e. 2023-24.

VII. FINDINGS

The following table 1.6 and the figure 1.6 shows the consolidated trend percentages of RIL fundamental Analysis during 2020-21 to 2024-25.

Table 1.6 Consolidated Statement showing the Trend Percentages of the RIL Fundamentals during the last Five years 2020-21 to 2024-25

S. No.	Fundamentals	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24	2024-25
1	Current	100	83.5	79.8	88.0	82.0
		0%	8%	5%	6%	9%
2	Sales	100	172.	215.	217.	210.
		0%	47%	05%	58%	59%

3	PAT	100	141.	155.	152.	127.
		0%	4%	63%	11%	58%
4	DPS	100	114.	128.	142.	78.5
		0%	29%	57%	86%	7%
5	Per Share Value	100	6.76	148.	93.3	3.63
		0%	%	09%	3%	%

Figure 1.6 Consolidated Trend Percentages for RIL Fundamentals during the last Five years 2020-21 to 2024-25

- The current ratio of the RIL is not satisfying the 2:1 ratio which is considered as the healthy financial status of a company. Because the reliance’s current ratio has a decreasing trend from 1.34 to 1.1 during the five financial years 2020-21 to 2024-2025. Thus the Reliance company is struggling to payout the debt with its current assets. The liability of the Reliance company is increasing than the assets of the company over the last 5 years.
- From the trend analysis of sales, it is found that the sales of the Reliance industries limited is increased up to first four financial years where as the trend percentage of sales decreased by 3.2%. It may be due to the low demand level over the

products of the reliance industries. As a result of the increase in demand (2022-2023 & 2023-24), the production has been increased to increase the inventories level. Thus the sales of the year 2022-23 is increased than the 2 previous years. It has been found that the demand may be increased due to the invention of the Telecommunication industries in the year 2022 – 2023.

- The trend of the profit of Reliance industries is attaining an increasing movement, which reveals the positive action of the company. Because of large capex in new energy & AI may weigh on short-term profits — execution risk exists. The analysis has found that there is a great difference between their profit to their DPS. Even though there is an increase in the net profit during the period of 2024-2025, such profits were used for other factors ignoring the wealth-maximization. The DPS is considered to have an adverse effect on the shareholders of the firm. Thus the net profit does not relate to the dividend distribution in the firm, creating a declination.
- The per share value of RIL found to be declined drastically during the last year i.e. 2024-25. It is mainly because the stock performance was driven by Jio growth, refining margins, retail expansion, and new energy strategy.

VIII. SUGGESTIONS

To improve the liquidity position of the company they may adopt the measure of selling the unproductive assets which are lying useless as fixed assets of the company. When those assets are sold, the cash balance of the company may go up and also the expenses in case of depreciation would also be eliminated. This may help the company to increase its cash and bank balances. The other measure could be the elimination of the long term debtors and converting them to be the short term receivables which could help for the immediate cash earning capacity of the company. The Reliance company have to focus on the wealth maximization than profit maximization. When the shareholders are benefited through the wealth maximization then automatically the share value of the company may increase in the market.

IX. CONCLUSION

Fundamental analysis is the strong theory accepted worldwide. Some investor strongly believes on fundamentals of company and some believe technical analysis plays very important role in investing. But it is mainly depending on demand and supply for the stocks in the stock market, an effort is made to make understand the investors about fundamental analysis by using the financial

data of the company. Reliance industries Ltd. have negative result in maintaining the solvency position and distribution of dividends to the shareholders. The financial profile points to solid governance, profitability, and controlled leverage, though ROE figures are moderate compared with pure growth tech firms. The profit of Reliance industries is increasing gradually which is a favourable sign to the company.

X. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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